

Protocol for conducting Systematic and Automated Aerial Surveys of Intertidal Communities Using Low-Cost Drones

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1. Objective.

This protocol aims at creating a standardized and replicable methodology for collecting periodic data regarding intertidal communities using low-cost and consumer-accessible drones while replicating the traditional methodology of ground-based photoquadrats. The work here described focuses on the planning and execution of automated flight missions in several sites to gather periodic data throughout the year. Additionally, this protocol was developed to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of low-cost drones for ecological intertidal research.

2. Equipment and Materials.

- UAS: drone + remote controller
- Smartphone
- GPS device
- Computer
- Drone Flight Control Software

3. Mission Planning

Low-cost drone selection

When conducting automated flights for surveying intertidal communities, selecting a low-cost drone with suitable features is essential. The selected drone should support an available Software Development Kit (SDK) to enable the integration of third-party apps, allowing for custom flight planning and data collection. Among the most cost-effective options (<800 €) are the DJI Mini Series (including the DJI Mini SE, DJI Mini 2, DJI Mini 3, and DJI Mini 3 Pro) and the DJI Air 2. Each one of these models offers distinct features and capabilities that may impact survey outcomes:

- 1. Camera Quality:** Different drones come equipped with several camera specifications, including resolution, sensor size, and stabilization features. Higher-resolution cameras are preferable for capturing detailed images of intertidal communities, aiding in accurate species identification and habitat assessment. Suitable gimbal mechanisms (3-axis) are also especially important to ensure correct photo positioning when conducting the missions.

2. **Flight Time:** Battery capacity is a critical factor, particularly when surveying larger areas. Drones with longer flight times can cover more ground per flight, reducing the need for frequent battery changes and enhancing data collection efficiency, but are also heavier and expensive. Having several batteries per site is a must for this type of work.
3. **Limitations and Capabilities:** Each drone has specific limitations, such as maximum wind resistance, altitude restrictions, speed, etc. Mini drones are more vulnerable to weather conditions, limiting the flights under certain circumstances. Understanding these factors is crucial for planning successful flights and ensuring data reliability.

The selected drone to test and optimize the protocol here described was the DJI MINI 3 Pro (<https://www.dji.com/pt/mini-3-pro>). This foldable and compact drone (24 cm wide, with a height of 7 cm) weighs only 249 grams, being placed under the lowest flight category according to the Portuguese Aviation Laws. The latest DJI updates enabled the integration of SDK (Software Development Kits) systems in its software, enhancing the possibility of the DJI Mini 3 Pro supporting third-party apps that might control its software. This drone is equipped with a 1/1.3-inch CMOS sensor that captures photographs in 48 MP mode with a resolution of 8064 × 6048 pixels and a focal length of 24 mm. Additionally, it features an automated trigger that captures a photo immediately after the arrival at the pre-set coordinates.

Figure 1. a) DJI MINI 3 Pro unfolded and with propellers placed. B) DJI MINI 3 Pro folded, showing how this drone offers an excellent capacity of being carried around with minimum effort.

GPS data collection

To effectively survey target areas within intertidal rocky shores using automated drone flights, it is necessary to collect accurate coordinates for further planning of the missions. To do so, it is recommended to use a suitable GPS capable of

collecting points with a precision of around <50 cm. For this work, the GPS used was a SparkFun RTK Facet L-Band® ([SparkFun GPS](#)). For each quadrat, the coordinates of the central point were collected with a 3 cm precision. The remaining 8 surrounding points were calculated using R and the geosphere package (v1.5-20; Hijmans, 2024) to save time overpassing the necessity of more data collection on the field (Figure 8b). These coordinates were then imported into the drone flight software to conduct the automated surveys.

Figure 2. a) GPS point distribution using the SparkFun RTK Facet L-Band; b) schematic demonstration of the coordinates obtained using R Studio. The point in red was the one obtained on the field using the high-precision GPS, and the coordinates of the other black dots were calculated using a script from R and the geosphere package.

Drone Flight Control Software: Setting up the Flights

To conduct the automated aerial surveys, it is necessary to plan the flights using specific drone flight control software. This kind of software acts as a third-party app enabled by the drone's Software Development Kit (SDK), which allows the control of various aspects of the flight process. The primary advantage of using these softwares is that we can now program and automate the flight path, ensuring consistent data collection and minimizing manual intervention. This is particularly useful when conducting repetitive surveys over time or at multiple locations, such as the monthly intertidal surveys designed based on this protocol.

There are several options regarding flight control software on the market, including DJI's Ground Station Pro, DroneDeploy, DroneLink, Pix4D, among others. Each of these offers the flexibility to program flight paths, manage the suitable survey coverage, and allows to automatically trigger the camera for consistent image capture. Selecting the right software will depend on the specific needs of the survey, such as site size (larger datasets require more advanced software), the level of

detail required, and the drone's compatibility. Ultimately, using such software ensures that aerial surveys are repeatable, standardized, and optimized for the study's objectives. For this project, DroneLink ([DroneLink Software](#)) was the software chosen due to its accessibility and ease of use. The coordinates of each point within the quadrat were placed in the Dronelink software so that the drone can fly to these exact locations and take a photo upon arrival. Several parameters were adjusted to optimize data collection according to the study's objectives:

- **Altitude:** Set height flight to 5/10 meters to achieve high-resolution imagery while maintaining sufficient coverage of each quadrat.
- **Gimbal Orientation:** -90° (nadiral), ensuring that the camera is oriented perpendicular to flight direction, minimizing distortion.
- **Speed:** Adjust according to the site's environmental conditions to maintain stability, ensure a suitable overlap of the images, and avoid distortion in photos while dictating the mission's duration.

These parameters enabled the consistent collection of imagery necessary for accurate analysis and comparison over time.

Figure 3. Planning of the drone missions using Dronelink. a) Interface of the software for programming the missions. b) Representation of the flight pattern of the drone above the quadrat previously selected. c) Image from one of the missions planned with the placement of the aerial photos in the mobile app.

Post-flight Data processing

After the data collection, it is necessary to process the photos for the creation of orthomosaics. To do so, it is necessary to use processing software capable of stitching together individual photos to produce a large, seamless representation of the study area. This process and the inherent creation of orthomosaics involve correcting geometric distortions that exist in the images and balancing the colors to ensure a correct and accurate representation of the region of interest. In this particular case, WebODM, an open-source software capable of processing large datasets in reasonable amounts of time, was used as the main tool for this crucial phase.

To achieve accurate results when generating the orthomosaics, the processing setup was adjusted, after several tests, to include the following options:

Figure 4. Processing of the images from one of the quadrats at Mindelo using WebODM. a) 3D model representing the reconstruction of the original photos; b) sequence of the photos taken by the drone in one of the quadrats of Mindelo; c) the quadrat location in the satellite map, showing the difference between what can be seen with Google Maps® and with the drone (better resolution and the area of interest is not submerged); d) the final orthomosaic created by WebODM, ready to be cropped and analyzed.

To carry out the processing phase, the nine photos collected for each quadrat must be uploaded to the selected software, with the options adjusted according to the research objectives, keeping in mind that higher-quality outputs require more processing time and more powerful computer features.

Figure 5. Data processing setup using WebODM. a) Creation of a new project. b) Upload the photos, set the parameters previously mentioned, and initiate the creation of orthomosaics.

After processing the original images, the output orthomosaics for each quadrat must be downloaded and stored for further analysis. Since there can be deviations in the drone's positioning, particularly during monthly or temporal surveys, further adjustments and cropping may be necessary to ensure that the images consistently represent the exact same area of interest. After this process, the data is ready to be analyzed. Repeting this process in different months will allow to assess species distribution and abundance, habitat structure, and ecological changes in these dynamic environments while creating a meaningful visual demonstration of these changes.

Survey Methodology: Step-by-step procedure

Mission Planning

- Selection of suitable sites for the aerial surveys;
- Collection of the central point coordinates for each quadrat using a GPS device;
- Calculation of the coordinates of the eight remaining points using an R Script or other programming technique;
- Program the survey missions using automated flight software and the pre-collected coordinates;
- Set flight altitude based on the area size and required resolution and the gimbal orientation to -90° to capture perpendicular photos as flat as possible;
- Ensure proper overlap in the images for effective analysis (minimum of 70% overlap);

Pre-flight preparation

- Check weather conditions and tide schedules and plan the days for the flights and in which months will the data collection occur;
- Ensure all equipment is charged and functional;
- Conduct a pre-flight check of the drone;

Data Collection: Flight

- Launch the drone at each site and let it follow the planned flight path automatically using the flight software.
- Set the drone to collect images upon arrival at each coordinate of the several quadrats in the intertidal area of interest;
- Set the drone to return home after the last photo collected;

Post-Flight Processing

- Download and organize collected data;
- Upload the imagery to photogrammetry software to create 3D models or orthomosaics;
- Conduct data analysis according to the study objectives (species identification, abundance estimation, grazing patches, etc.) using manual annotation and automated classifiers;

Monthly data collection

- Repeat the process in the following months and compare the analyzed data to track temporal changes in the target communities;

4. Conclusion

After the conclusion of the procedure, it is possible to obtain several orthomosaics that can provide detailed visual records of the intertidal regions, allowing for precise analysis of spatial and temporal changes in the study area. The consistency of the drone surveys using this protocol enabled the detection of fine-scale variations in substrate composition, vegetation cover, and the distribution of intertidal organisms. This approach can facilitate the identification of seasonal patterns and potential long-term trends, offering new insights into the dynamics of these complex ecosystems.

Several orthomosaics can be created for each quadrat at all locations desired across different sites and arranged side by side to illustrate temporal variations throughout the year as shown in **Figure 6**. Besides that, it is also possible to create timelapses in GIF format for each one of the quadrats, generating an elucidative display of the seasonal variances happening throughout the year to these communities.

Figure 6. Final output for 7 months of data collection and orthomosaic creation for the three tidal levels (a) Top; (b) Mid; and (c) Low, in Mindelo, Portugal.

Applying this protocol enables the development of an efficient workflow for periodic data collection, allowing for the acquisition of meaningful imagery on a monthly or annual basis, while also serving as a foundation for future studies and ecological research focused on intertidal communities or other ecosystem types.

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